

Potential Benefits of *Matricaria chamomilla* in Diabetes Mellitus Complications: Integrative Review

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic disease characterized by persistente hyperglycemia. The clinical complications of Diabetes are varied and may include cardiovascular repercussions, diabetic neuropathy, diabetic retinopathy, diabetic nephropathy and immune system problems, among others. In the context of DM treatment, it is important that alternative approaches emerge that can complement or even replace conventional therapy. *Matricaria chamomilla* has antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and hypoglycemic properties and may be beneficial in the control of DM. The study is based on the integrative literature review method, which aims to gather, analyze and synthesize the main relevant research on the topic. The following descriptors were used to search for the articles: *Matricaria chamomilla* and Diabetes mellitus taken from DeCS, which were collected from the Pubmed, Web of Science and Virtual Health Library (VHL) databases, with a time frame of the last 10 years from the year 2013. Six of 32 articles were selected for the review. It was found in the articles that *M. chamomilla* exerts action on the main characteristics of Diabetes, with antihyperglycemic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, healing effect, in addition to cardiac and renal protection, the species exerts action on cognitive improvement. The experimental studies on the effects of *M. chamomilla* on Diabetes provide some promising evidence, suggesting potential benefits in relation to various aspects of the disease. However, it is important to note that most of these studies have been conducted in animal models of diabetes, and translating these results to humans requires well-designed clinical trials.

Additional keywords: Flavonoids; Anti-hyperglycemic activity; Kidney and Cardiac Protection; Cognitive Improvement.

RESUMO

Potenciais Benefícios da *Matricaria chamomilla* nas complicações da Diabetes mellitus: Revisão integrativa

O Diabetes mellitus é uma doença crônica caracterizada por hiperglicemia. As complicações clínicas do Diabetes são variadas e podem incluir repercussões cardiovasculares, neuropatia diabética, retinopatia diabética, nefropatia diabética e problemas no sistema imunológico, entre outras. No contexto do tratamento do DM é importante que surjam abordagens alternativas que possam complementar ou até mesmo substituir a terapia convencional. A *Matricaria chamomilla* possui propriedades antioxidantes, anti-inflamatórias e hipoglicêmicas, podendo vir a ser benéfica no controle do DM. O estudo utiliza como base o método de revisão da literatura integrativa, que tem como finalidade reunir, analisar e sintetizar as principais pesquisas relevantes sobre o tema. Foi utilizado os seguintes descritores para a busca dos artigos: *Matricaria chamomilla* e Diabetes Mellitus retirados do DeCS, que foram coletados dos bancos de dados Pubmed, Web of Science e Biblioteca Virtual em Saúde (BVS), com recorte temporal dos últimos 10 anos a partir do ano de 2013. Foram selecionados 6, de 32 artigos, para a revisão. Foram encontrados nos artigos que a *M. chamomilla* exerce ação nas principais características do Diabetes, com efeito anti-hiperglicêmico, anti-inflamatório, antioxidante, cicatrizante, além da

proteção cardíaca e renal, a espécie exerce ação na melhora cognitiva. Os estudos experimentais sobre os efeitos da *M. chamomilla* no Diabetes fornecem algumas evidências promissoras, sugerindo potenciais benefícios em relação a vários aspectos da doença. No entanto, é importante notar que a maioria desses estudos foi realizada em modelos animais de diabetes, e a translação desses resultados para seres humanos requer estudos clínicos bem projetados.

Palavras-chave adicionais: Flavonóides; Atividade Anti-hiperglicêmica; Proteção Renal e Cardíaca; Melhora cognitiva.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes *mellitus* (DM) is a chronic disease characterized by high blood glucose levels due to insufficient insulin production or the body's inability to adequately use the available insulin (Dao *et al.*, 2023). This condition can result in significant epidemiological complications, affecting various organs and systems of the human body (Liu *et al.*, 2023).

The epidemiological complications of DM are varied and may include cardiovascular disease, diabetic neuropathy, diabetic retinopathy, diabetic nephropathy and problems in the immune system, among others (Araújo, 2022). These complications can have a significant impact on patients' quality of life and increase the risk of morbidity and mortality (Gui *et al.*, 2023).

In the context of DM treatment, alternative approaches are emerging that can complement or even replace conventional therapy (Wang *et al.*, 2023). A commonly studied medicinal plant for this purpose is *M. chamomilla*, also known as chamomile. Chamomile has antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and hypoglycemic properties, which may be beneficial in the management of DM (Cemek *et al.*, 2008).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study used as a strategy the integrative literature review method, which aims to review approach that seeks to gather, analyze and synthesize all relevant research on a given topic, regardless of its methodological approach. This analysis seeks the contribution to the development of the theme in the available evidence.

Data Collect

The articles, with the descriptors *M. chamomilla* and DM taken from DeCS, were collected from the scientific databases Pubmed, Web of Science and Virtual Health Library (VHL), with a temporal cut of the last 10 years from the year 2013.

To facilitate the literature search process, the definition of the theme of the work followed the PICO format, a tool commonly used to designate the research question (Liberatiet *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, the selection criteria for the studies were: 1) Population, animals induced to DM and/or diabetic humans; 2) Intervention, use of phytotherapy and/or medicinal plants; 3) Control, comparative groups without use of phytotherapy and/or medicinal plants; 4) Outcome, improvement of DM symptoms; 5) Type of study, randomized clinical trials, cross-sectional and prospective studies, and/or experimental models. The PICO question is described in Table 1.

RESULTS

Summary of the articles found

It was found 10 articles in Pubmed, 9 articles in Web of Science and 11 articles in the BVS, with the search "*Matricaria chamomilla*" AND "Diabetes Mellitus", among them 6 articles were selected that were in accordance with the inclusion criteria for the present study.

Characteristics of the study

Study modelo

There are different models of diabetes induction in rats, each with its own characteristics and different mechanisms. Some of the most commonly used models are: Streptozotocin (STZ)-induced DM model; Alloxan-induced DM model; Diet-induced DM model; Genetically modified DM model (Radenković *et al.*, 2015; Mostafavinia *et al.*, 2016).

Streptozotocin is a chemical substance that selectively destroys the beta cells of the pancreas, which are responsible for producing insulin. Administration of STZ to rats causes a significant reduction in insulin production, leading to the development of type 1 DM. This model is widely used to study the pathogenesis and test new

Table 1 – Description of the PICO question.

	Descrição
Population	DM patients (any type) and/or animals (any species) induced with DM characteristics.
Intervention	Use of extracts from the <i>M. chamomilla</i> plant and/or phytotherapy and/or molecules extracted from the plant as an adjuvant treatment for DM (any dose).
Control	Placebo control interventions, no treatment with herbal medicine and/or <i>M. chamomilla</i> , and/or a comparator drug for the intervention.
Outcome	Improvements in DM symptoms such as hyperglycemia, cognitive impairment and oxidative stress parameters.
Type of study	Randomized, crossover, double-blind placebo-controlled clinical trials, prospective and/or experimental studies.

Figure 1 – Identification of estudies based on the flow chart.

Source: Adapted and translated from PRISMA 2020.

Table 2 – Articles found for the study

	Title	Author/Year	Result
1.	Chamomile tea improves glycemic indices and antioxidants status in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus.	Zemestani, <i>et al.</i> 2015.	Anti-hyperglycemic Anti-inflammatory Antioxidant
2.	Chamomile and oregano extracts synergistically exhibit antihyperglycemic, antihyperlipidemic, and renal protective effects in alloxan-induced diabetic rats.	Prasanna, <i>et al.</i> 2017.	Anti-hyperglycemic Anti-hyperlipidemic Kidney Protector
3.	Attenuation of inflammation in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rabbits by <i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> oil: A focus on targeting NF- κ B and NLRP3 signaling pathways.	Saghahazrati, <i>et al.</i> 2019.	Anti-hyperglycemic Anti-inflammatory Antioxidant
4.	<i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> Extract Improves Diabetic Wound Healing in Rat Models.	Nematollahi, <i>et al.</i> 2019.	Anti-hyperglycemic Healing Effect
5.	The potential cardioprotective effect of <i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> extract against diabetes-induced oxidative stress in rats.	Soliman, <i>et al.</i> 2020.	Anti-hyperglycemic Cardiac Protector
6.	Ameliorative effects of endurance training and <i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> flowers hydroethanolic extract on cognitive deficit in type 2 diabetes rats.	Heidarianpour, <i>et al.</i> 2021.	Anti-hyperglycemic Cognitive improvement

treatments for type 1 DM (Kottaisamy *et al.*, 2021; Araujo, 2022).

Alloxan is another chemical that causes damage to the beta cells of the pancreas. Its administration in rats results in a reduction in insulin production and the development of type 1 DM. This model is similar to the STZ induction model and is frequently used in studies of type 1 DM (Araujo, 2022).

The diet-induced diabetes model involves the administration of a high-fat or high-fat and carbohydrate diet for a prolonged period (Labre *et al.*, 2022). High-calorie and inadequate feeding can lead to obesity; insulin resistance and the development of type 2 DM in rats (Poblete-Jara *et al.*, 2023). This model is used to study the mechanisms underlying the development of type 2 DM and to evaluate therapeutic interventions (Poblete-Jara *et al.*, 2023).

The present study did not limit the animal models in the inclusion criteria. Three models of the articles found were identified, both preclinical and clinical. A variedade de modelos, além de sustentar melhor as buscas conceituais na revisão integrativa, potencializa diferentes avaliações de forma eficiente dos efeitos apresentados da *M. chamomilla*.

Varieties of Extracts

Four different types of extracts were identified in

the selected articles, namely: tea, essential oil, gel, hydroethanolic and dried forms.

Tea extract: Tea extract is prepared by infusing or decocting the leaves, flowers or other components of a plant in hot water. This method is commonly used to extract water-soluble compounds such as polyphenols, flavonoids and catechins. The tea can be consumed as a beverage or used topically in skin preparations (Wiese, 2023).

Essential oil: Essential oil is obtained from steam distillation or cold pressing of plant parts such as leaves, flowers, bark or roots. This process concentrates the volatile and aromatic compounds of the plant in liquid form (Lima *et al.*, 2018). Essential oils are composed by a variety of components, including terpenes and terpenoids, which confer aromatic and therapeutic properties. Essential oils can be used in aromatherapy, massage, personal care products and in some medicinal applications (Alves-Soares *et al.*, 2022).

Gel extract: Gel extract is a type of extract obtained by combining a plant extract with a gelatinous base. This base can be made of carbomers, gums or natural gels. The gel extract is often used in cosmetic and dermatological products due to its pleasant texture and ability to gradually release the active compounds into the skin (Sallustio *et al.*, 2023).

Hydroethanolic extract of the flower: The

hydroethanolic extract is prepared by extracting a plant into a solution of water and ethanol (alcohol). This type of extract is able to extract a variety of compounds, including those soluble in water and in alcohol. The hydroethanolic extract of the flower can be used in cosmetic products, herbal medicines and in scientific research to evaluate the pharmacological activity of the compounds present in the plant (Park *et al.*, 2021).

Qualitative analysis of the studies

The data from the experiments were evaluated taking into account their methodology, which includes criteria such as the approval of the animal research ethics committee, an appropriate analysis and interpretation of the data, in addition to checking for possible conflicts of interest. When there were any differences in the data, they were checked with the corresponding authors of the papers.

DISCUSSION

Anti-hyperglycemic effect

Hyperglycemia is a central feature of DM (Heidarianpour *et al.*, 2021). Patients with diabetes have difficulty in adequately controlling their blood glucose levels, either due to insulin resistance, or lack of insulin production by the pancreas (Chang *et al.*, 2023).

An antihyperglycemic effect occurs when a treatment or substance is able to reduce the concentration of glucose in the blood, restoring it to levels closer to optimal. This is usually achieved by improving insulin sensitivity, increasing glucose uptake by cells or reducing glucose production by the liver (Popovicu *et al.*, 2023).

In the context of *M. chamomilla*, articles demonstrate that it may have an antihyperglycemic effect (Zemestani *et al.*, 2015; Prasanna *et al.*, 2017; Saghahazrati *et al.*, 2019; Soliman *et al.*, 2020). Article 2 demonstrated that the diabetic group treated with Mc, at doses of 150 and 300 mg/kg, significantly reduced ($p < 0.05$) both serum glucose levels and glycated hemoglobin concentration and increased serum insulin levels ($p < 0.05$) (Prasanna, 2017).

Compared to normal rabbits, Article 3 demonstrated that STZ-induced diabetic rabbits exhibited significantly increased blood glucose levels and reduced serum insulin levels that were reversed using medium and high tested doses of *M. chamomilla* oil. Likewise, STZ-induced diabetic rabbits showed a significant increase in NF- κ B and NLRP3 protein expression in pancreatic tissue that was reversed by the tested high dose of *M. chamomilla* oil (Saghahazrati *et al.*, 2019).

Anti-hyperlipidemic effect

In DM, hyperlipidemia is one of the common complications and is associated with a higher risk of cardiovascular diseases, which are one of the main causes of morbidity and mortality in patients with DM (Chait & den Hartigh, 2020).

An antihyperlipidemic effect occurs when a treatment or substance is able to reduce blood lipid levels, either by decreasing lipid production by the liver, increasing lipid excretion, or improving lipid metabolism. These effects help to improve the lipid profile and reduce the risk of cardiovascular complications associated with hyperlipidemia.

Quanto ao efeito anti-hiperlipidêmico da *M. chamomilla* no contexto do DM, é descrito pelo pelos artigos achados que a camomila pode

Table 3 - Characteristics of the studies found.

Model	Induction	Type extract of Mc/ Dosage	Treatment (Days)
1. Humans (Men and Women)	DM2	Tea /3 g/150 ml	56
2. Wistar Rats (Male)	ALX120mg/kg (i.p)	Parched/150 and 300 mg/kg	21 and 42
Albino rabbits	STZ 80mg/kg (i.p)	Essential oil/25, 50 and 100 mg/kg	21
3. Wistar Rats (Male)	Diet and STZ 50mg/kg (i.p)	Gel/ 5% and 10%	15
4. Wistar Rats (Male)	Diet and STZ 45mg/kg (i.p)	Flower Hydroethanolic/200 and 400mg/kg	70
5. Wistar Rats (Male)	Diet and STZ 65mg/kg (i.p)	Flower Hydroethanolic /200 mg/kg	84

Streptozotocin (STZ); Intraperitoneal (i.p); Alloxan (ALX); Diabetes mellitus 2 type (DM2); Matricaria chamomilla (Mc).

reduzir a atividade lipídêmica do DM (Prassana, 2015). In Article 1, a significant reduction ($p < 0.05$) of triglyceride and total cholesterol levels was demonstrated, in addition to an improvement in lipid profiles.

Anti-inflammatory effect

Chronic inflammation has been implicated in the pathogenesis of DM and is associated with related complications such as insulin resistance, pancreatic beta-cell dysfunction and tissue damage (Rohm *et al.*, 2022).

The reduction of the inflammatory response in the body, such as the decrease in the production of inflammatory cytokines, the activation of inflammatory cells and the expression of inflammatory mediators, is a physiological and pharmacological resource to prevent a systemic aggravation (Solanki *et al.*, 2023).

Regarding *M. chamomilla*, studies point to its anti-inflammatory properties (Zemestani *et al.*, 2015; Saghahazrati, 2019). These studies showed that chamomile extract can reduce DM-related inflammation in tissues such as adipose tissue and pancreas, and modulate the production of inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-6 (IL-6) and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF-alpha) (Saghahazrati *et al.*, 2019).

Anti-oxidative effect

Free radicals are unstable molecules that can cause cell damage when in excess, contributing to the development and progression of several diseases, including DM. The damage caused by these radicals triggers a cascade of biochemical activations and inhibitions, increasing the oxidative stress of the tissue being damaged (Gerber & Rutter, 2019; Darenskaya *et al.*, 2021; Yi *et al.*, 2023).

Oxidative stress, in the context of DM, has a significant role in the pathogenesis of the disease, causing damage to beta-pancreatic cells, decreasing insulin sensitivity and contributing to related complications such as cardiovascular disease and kidney damage (Saghahazrati, 2019; Zemestani *et al.*, 2015).

The ability of a substance or treatment to neutralize free radicals in the body and protect cells against oxidative stress is called the antioxidant effect and has been at the forefront of research into a wide range of diseases, including DM (Kang & Yang, 2020).

An antioxidant effect occurs when a substance is able to neutralize free radicals, stabilizing them and preventing their harmful reactivity (Gerber & Rutter, 2019). This can be achieved by increasing endogenous antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase and glutathione peroxidase, or by acting directly as an antioxidant agent.

Regarding *M. chamomilla*, it is demonstrated in the literature that its components, mainly flavonoids such as apigenin and luteolin, have antioxidant properties (Yi *et al.*, 2023). These studies have shown that they can increase endogenous antioxidant enzymes and protect cells against oxidative damage (Kang & Yang, 2020).

The selected articles follow what the literature directs, suggesting that, regardless of the extract studied, *M. chamomilla* and its components cause antioxidant effects (Saghahazrati, 2019; Zemestani *et al.*, 2015). Article number 1 demonstrated that chamomile tea, in addition to controlling glycemic levels in humans, also increased the levels of antioxidant enzymes, such as malondialdehyde, catalase, superoxide dismutase and glutathione oxidase, in patients with type 2 DM (Saghahazrati, 2019; Zemestani *et al.*, 2015).

Heart and kidney protection

The complexity of the damage caused by DM is further exacerbated when it impairs the functioning of systemic organs, like heart, liver and kidney (Hammoud & Drucker, 2023). Complications in these organs affect the full functioning of the entire body, worsening the condition of these patients (Hwang, 2023).

The need to mitigate the harmful effects that the disease causes on systemic organs has become a priority in coping with DM, especially in patients who are at risk of developing or have already developed other comorbidities (Yang *et al.*, 2023).

Article number 5 points out that chamomile extract may have cardioprotective properties. This study demonstrated that *M. chamomilla* reduced the serum levels of cardiac tissue injury biomarkers, such as AST, LDH, CK, CK-MB, cTnI, in the diabetic groups induced by STZ and treated with doses of 200 mg/kg and 400 mg /kg of hydroethanolic extract of *M. chamomilla* (Soliman *et al.*, 2020).

Literature points out the possible

vasodilator effects that *M. chamomilla* and its components may have (Hwang, 2023). These effects, together with the decreases in the expression of cardiac tissue biomarkers presented in article number 5, demonstrate possible cardioprotective advantages, improving cardiac function and decreasing the risk of cardiovascular complications associated with DM.

Regarding to renal protection, some studies in animal models of DM suggest that chamomile may offer renal benefits (Roozbeh et al., 2013; Santos et al., 2023). The Article 1 study showed that chamomile may help attenuate kidney dysfunction associated with diabetes by reducing oxidative stress, inflammation and the accumulation of advanced glycation end products in the kidneys (Prassana, 2017). These effects may help preserve kidney function and prevent the development of diabetes-related kidney complications. However, just as in cardiovascular protection, more research, including human clinical studies, is needed to fully confirm and understand these renal effects of chamomile in DM (Prassana, 2017; Soliman, 2023).

Healing effect

Healing in patients with DM can be a complex and slower process compared to non-diabetic individuals (Lin et al., 2023). This is due to various metabolic and vascular changes associated with the disease. In DM, elevated blood glucose levels can negatively affect blood vessel and nerve function, impairing proper circulation and local immune response (Sun et al., 2023).

DM leads to micro and macrovascular complications, such as peripheral arterial disease and diabetic neuropathy, which can affect nutrition and sensitivity in the wound area, making healing difficult and, in some more complicated cases, even causing amputations (Xiong et al., 2023).

M. chamomilla and its components may have an effect that enhances healing (Nematollahi et al., 2019; Niknam et al., 2021). Article 4 concluded that the results of the studies revealed that *M. chamomilla* gel has the ability to improve the wound healing process in diabetic rats, increasing the number of fibroblasts and the vascularization of the damaged tissue (Nematollahi et al., 2019).

Cognitive Function

DM has been associated with changes in cognitive

function, especially in cases of long-term and poorly controlled diabetes (Roy et al., 2023). As stated, chronic hyperglycemia, can cause damage to blood vessels and nerves, including those present in the brain. These changes can affect cognitive function such as memory, learning, attention and other mental abilities (He et al., 2023). In addition, DM is also associated with a higher risk of developing cerebrovascular diseases, such as stroke and Alzheimer's disease (Camm et al., 2023; Hamzé et al., 2023; Shen et al., 2023). These conditions can have a negative impact on cognitive function and lead to memory and cognition difficulties (Roy et al., 2023).

Article number 6 showed cognitive improvement in STZ-induced diabetic rats treated with hydroethanolic extract of *M. chamomilla* (Heidarianpour et al., 2021). In this article, the impact of exercise and *M. chamomilla* on cognitive impairment in diabetes yielded significant results ($p < 0.05$).

Overall, the results of this study showed that resistance training combined with *M. chamomilla* extract could significantly modulate cell death caused by diabetes in the CA3 region of the hippocampus (Heidarianpour et al., 2021). The use of exercise and *M. chamomilla* interventions may have protective effects against diabetic neuropathy, and suggest a new treatment perspective to prevent hippocampal nerve cell death and cognitive impairment caused by diabetes. The prospects for improving the cognitive function of treated rats were positive (Heidarianpour et al., 2021).

In addition to presenting a decrease in oxidative stress, which is related to cognitive deficits, treatment with *M. chamomilla* prevented necrosis of hippocampal cells in these diabetic rats. However, regarding the effect of *M. chamomilla* on cognitive function in patients with diabetes, the evidence is limited and needs further research (Heidarianpour et al., 2021; Nivins & Klingberg, 2023).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Experimental studies on the effects of *M. chamomilla* on DM provide some promising evidence, suggesting potential benefits in relation to various aspects of the disease. However, it is important to note that most of these studies were conducted in animal models of diabetes, and

translating these results to humans requires well-designed clinical trials.

Furthermore, it is critical to remember that diabetes is a complex and chronic condition that requires a multidisciplinary approach for proper treatment and management. Proper control of blood glucose levels, along with a balanced diet, regular physical activity and the use of prescribed medications, remains the cornerstone of diabetes treatment.

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